

Dr. Anthony Dunne **Design noir***

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When the Sony Walkman was introduced in the early 1980s it offered people a new kind of relationship to urban space. It allowed the wearer to create their own portable micro-environment, and it provided a soundtrack for travel through the city encouraging different readings of familiar settings. It functioned as an urban interface.

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Fifteen years on there are hundreds of variations on the appearance of the Walkman but the relationship it created to the city remains the same. This scenario reflects how product designers have responded to the aesthetic challenge of electronic technology. They have accepted a role as a semiotician, a companion of packaging designers and marketeers, creating semiotic skins for incomprehensible technologies. The electronic product accordingly occupies a strange place in the world of material culture, closer to washing powder and cough mixture than furniture and architecture.

But this is just one approach to product design, one genre if you like, which offers a very limited experience. Like a Hollywood movie its emphasis is on easy pleasure and conformist values. It reinforces the status quo rather than challenging it. There could be so many other genres of product: eg arthouse, porn, horror, noir even, that exploit the unique and exciting functional and aesthetic potential of electronic technology.

Design genres

An occasional glance through almost any tabloid newspaper reveals a view of everyday life where complex emotions, desires and needs are played out through the misuse and abuse of electronic products and systems. A mother shoots her son after an argument over which television channel to watch; the police set a trap for scanner snoopers (people who listen illegally to emergency radio frequencies) by broadcasting a message that an UFO has landed in a local forest (within minutes several cars arrive and their scanners are confiscated); a parent is outraged by a speaking doll, made in China, which sounds like it swears. Yet even though industrial design plays a part in the design of extreme pain (eg weapons) and pleasure (eg sex aids) the range of emotions offered through most electronic products is pathetically narrow. More diverse design genres could offer more complex and

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demanding aesthetic experiences by referring to this bizarre world of the 'infra-ordinary', where stories show that truth is indeed stranger than fiction, and that our experience of everyday day life lived through conventional electronic products is aesthetically impoverished.

The Truth Phone by the Counter Spy Shop, a real product, is an example of how a design noir product might work. It combines a voice stress analyser with a telephone, and shows how electronic products have the potential to generate a chain of events which together form a story. If you consider products in this way the design shifts from concerns of physical interaction (passive button pushing), to the potential psychological experiences inherent in the product. The user becomes a protagonist and the designer becomes a co-author of the experience. Imagine speaking to your mother or a

lover while the Truth Phone suggests they are lying: the product creates dilemmas rather than resolving them. By using it the owner explores boundaries between themselves and the paranoid user suggested by the product. They enter into a psychological adventure.

What I'm proposing, is that product designers could become more like authors. They could draw from the narrative potential of electronic product misuse and abuse to create alternative notions of use and need, rather than the official images of how people live with technology. Instead of thinking about appearance, user friendliness or corporate identity, industrial designers could propose new products which are more challenging. The

Truth Phone looks like any other slick matt black mainstream phone; but it is through using it, or interacting with its paranoid logic, that its real aesthetic is revealed. You won't become paranoid by using it, but you might experience a routine phone call from a paranoid person's perspective. Aesthetics of mis-use

In 1994 the British mobile phone company Cellnet produced a booklet, *Mobile Moments: A Collection of Tales for the '90s*, a chronicle of events which, it felt, demonstrated the crucial part the mobile phone has come to play in our lives. The tales are arranged under headings such as *Mating by Mobile*, *Mobile Heroes*, *Mobile Marvels* and, most interestingly, *Mobile Mishaps*. Each story is an example of the narrative space entered by mis-using a simple electronic product, of how electronic technologies can generate rich experiences that challenge the conformity of everyday life by short-circuiting our emotions and states of mind. I am suggesting not that designers try to predict misuses of electronic products, but rather that they refer, as a wider context of use, to the possibilities of the unofficial and the unexpected, instead of standard behavioural models.

Conceptual design

We are surrounded by products that give us an illusion of choice and encourage passivity, yet we could have so much more. Different genres of electronic products could enrich and expand our experience of everyday life rather than closing it down. Industrial design's position at the heart of consumer culture, (after all, it is fuelled by the capitalist system), could be subverted for more socially beneficial ends by enriching our experiences. It could provide a unique aesthetic language that engages the viewer in ways a film might, without being utopian or prescribing how things ought to be.

But developing alternative genres of electronic product is made difficult by the fact that industrial designers see the social value of their work as inextricably linked to the marketplace. Design outside this arena is viewed with suspicion as escapist or unreal. At the moment, the only alternatives to the Hollywood genre of design are 'concept designs' from earnest but inexperienced students or design consultancies promoting themselves to corporate clients.

Truly radical alternatives could really only exist outside the marketplace, as a form of 'conceptual design'- meaning not the conceptual stage of a design project, but a product intended to challenge preconceptions about how electronics shape our lives. Designers would need to explore how such design thinking might re-enter everyday life in ways that maintain the design proposal's critical integrity and effectiveness while facing criticism of escapism, utopianism or fantasy. The challenge is to blur the boundaries between the real and the fictional, so that the conceptual becomes more real and the real is seen as just one limited possibility.

So how could alternative genres of product that challenge the Hollywood vision of large corporations be developed?

One way this could happen is if design developed its own independent vision, and worked with the public to demand more from industry. But this would require not only a shift in the way designers view their position, but also how design organisations see their role. They would need, like the Architecture Foundation in London, or the Netherlands Design Institute perhaps, to encourage diverse visions through competitions and workshops for practising designers, and engage the public through more challenging exhibitions and publications.

Architecture could also play a part in this debate. It has a well established forum for exploring and communicating alternative visions of how life might be, but despite research in the 1960s by Archigram and others, it still struggles to get to grips with how electronic technology embodied in mass-produced products like mobile phones and Global Positioning Systems impacts on traditional architectural and urban experiences. But it is only a matter of time before a new generation of architects start to formulate new visions that include electronic products.

Or, is this a role best left to 'academic' designers - free from commercial restrictions and based in an educational environment.

Rather than writing papers and seeking conventional academic approval, they could exploit their privileged position to explore a subversive role for design as social critique, developing provocative design genres to challenge the simplistic Hollywood vision of the consumer electronics industry?